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Rach of Aegis: Beyond David Helfgott

By Marianne Uszler

I can hear you groan. It is an unforgivable pun. But I'd like to make a point. The point is not original (can anything new possibly be written about Helfgott?), but the torrent of words—most of them hyperbolic and emotionally charged—about this man, and this concerto, causes all serious pianists to be in turns astonished, queasy, and affronted. We can't just look the other way. We need to answer something, define something, pinpoint something, if only—perhaps especially—among ourselves.

So many things are unsettling in this rampant soap-operatic spectacle. Were it just the film, I think that few of us would be upset, and many would applaud. It's a provocative and compelling story. We might not even have quibbled with the film score, which is just as fragmentary and inflated as much else that accompanies visual images and dramatic actions. No, it's the CD and the concert tour that's got us riled. It's the "real" David Helfgott that arouses the furor and indignation. That, and the fact that legitimate critical opinion is lampooned by the general press as being sniping, petty, and negligible. We come off sounding like poor losers.

On this page I communicate with a special group. In *P&K* the talk is "just among us" pianists. I'm not trying to meet the public head-on, nor would I be so rash as to plumb any psychiatric depths. I won't even attempt to speak to the so-called "human issues" which are as painful and uplifting as everyone says they are. The matter to which I think we need to pay attention is the "aegis" more than the "Rach." The concerto, and Rachmaninoff, will remain unaffected. But the piano recital—its purpose as well as its spirit—has been sensationalized. Will life after *Shine* (at least for pianists) be compromised or enhanced?

Aegis is a word used infrequently these days—we're more apt to talk about "PR" and "backers" and "spin." Not that aegis means the same as any of those expressions, but the ideas behind these phenomena often get blurred. Aegis means sponsorship, of course. But it is curious that the original meaning was "shield" (such as those worn by the Greek gods), and therefore the earliest use of the word signified protection. Odd, isn't it, that a word denoting protection has come to mean almost its opposite?

What has been packaged for Helfgott is what we wish would be available for those who really are great artists—a big tour, soldout houses, excited crowds, dizzying record sales, reams of print, avid TV crews, not to mention the carloads of money. It happened, as we all know, not because of Helfgott the pianist, but because his life struggle is a gripping story and has, moreover, become a powerful film. Once again the movies have created a "phantom" (again in the guise of hero), a person who doesn't really exist, much like John Wayne or Humphrey Bogart (who were real people, of course, but whose images were not). Whomever Helfgott the person really is, the public is being duped into accepting him as something that he is not.

That is the downside of aegis and promotion. Selling the performer becomes the end. The performer becomes a commodity whose identity is eclipsed—as Helfgott himself mutters, "Image image image image." This is a problem much larger than the *Shine* phenomenon. It has to do with the marketing of serious music in the broadest sense. Performing artists have always needed to face the challenge of image or notoriety. (Some performers fill halls just because they are names, no matter what, or how, they play.) The recording industry and radio disc jockeys often dictate, not just influence, what music and which performers cut CDs and get air time. (Russell Ferrante speaks about this very subject in the interview on page 26.)

So we're back to the question I posed at the outset. What should be our reaction to the Helfgott hoopla? Reactionary indignation is not enough. That's tilting at windmills. Perhaps *P&K* can be a forum in which pianists (and managers and promoters?) deal with the issues of career management. Leave Rach to the ages. ❖

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Join the Army and Play the Piano!

By Joseph Holt

SFC Mike Tisdale

The "Perfectly Patriotic Pianists" are (from left) SFC Arthur Poulin, SSG Raffi Kasparian, SSG Joseph Holt, and Major John Clanton (conductor of the United States Army Chorus). They were showcased in a multi-piano event with the United States Army Band.

Most pianists are trained with the same objective in mind—to become concert keyboard artists. We practice etudes, scales, sonatas, character pieces, and concertos while preparing for a multitude of competitions and a lifetime of public performance. From the earliest lessons through conservatory training, we develop the requisite technical skills while refining interpretative insights that illuminate performances, sharing with audiences our vision, temperament, passion for music, and experiences.

Many pianists pursue concert careers through competitions and auditions for

performance spots on concert series. Some pursue further degree studies. A few are able to sustain successful concert careers with performances around the world, and many also combine teaching with performing. Other pianists might be entirely devoted to teaching, accompanying, or playing chamber music, while some might enjoy being rehearsal pianists for a chorus, local opera company, or musical theater organization. The choices are endless, limited only by interest and ability. One fact, however, is very clear in this late 20th-century world—there are few opportunities for concert pianists, but the potential for working as a pianist/musician is overwhelming.

The piano is one of the most versatile instruments ever developed. But are pianists trained to be versatile? Being *totally* versatile is somewhat impractical and foolish, but our training should more accurately reflect current performing conditions and adequately prepare us for realistic potential careers. Other instrumentalists are trained not only as soloists, but as orchestral and chamber musicians; singers learn opera roles and lieder, but also participate in ensembles. Pianists seem to be the only group with a single focus. Is this realistic? Why do we concentrate so much effort on developing the resources necessary for a solo concert career when the opportunities for obtaining and maintaining such a career are very slim?

Virtuoso pianists have dominated the musical scene for a long time. While the draw to this glamorous career often begins at an early age, statistics show that the majority of us, although trained as concert pianists, are destined for careers that include only a few concerts, with some teaching and several other musical jobs thrown in for good measure. The greatest challenge that pianists face is how to make a living in the current marketplace. Some pianists even abandon the music business and explore entirely different careers. (An interesting cultural study would be to compare those with arts degrees that actually work in the arts with those who have received an arts degree but now work in non-related fields.)

The idea of having a multifaceted career as a pianist is rooted in reality. With a degree in piano, you are able to pursue many different types of musical careers. My early childhood dream to play piano concertos with orchestras has transformed and unfolded into a career that includes many (but not all, by any means) of the positions listed in the sidebar. The choices that I have made reflect a basic desire in my professional life—to play the piano and make music. Sometimes the avenues taken were not quite where I wanted to be, but the experiences have always been rewarding and enriching. They have expanded my horizons, put me in touch with a greater circle of professional contacts, and stimulated wonderful friendships. How did I get there?

The basic elements that serve as guide, underlying support, and framework for my daily work are few. These include being able to sight-read almost any piece of music with conviction, a thorough understanding of keyboard theory and harmony, a good solid technique, and a quick memory. Coupled with a love for music that extends beyond keyboard literature, developing specialized keyboard skills such as score reading and transposition, getting a smattering of experience in conducting and composition, and participating in a variety of musical activities has been a logical development. I am wholly indebted to the many teachers who have imparted to me their wisdom, understanding of music, and love for the instrument.

My formation as a pianist began with theory instruction before actual keyboard lessons. Because we didn't have a piano at home, Bette Chambless taught me to read and understand music notation before introducing me to the piano. As a result, reading music at the piano was somewhat easier when I actually started to play. This became the basis for my ability to sight-read, and it has been fundamental to my career. Bob Chambless was the church music director, and he taught the basics of music which served as an introduction to music theory, harmony, and ear training. I'm convinced that this early training gave me much needed tools for understanding and enjoying music. Lessons on the viola, an instrument for which I had no particular talent, were also part of my early training. Learning to read the alto clef from an early age prepared me for reading orchestral scores.

While at the Eastman School of Music, my ability to sight-read meant that I was selected, among others, to assist in the annual school auditions. My task consisted of working with the applicants who were singers, helping them to prepare a 15-minute audition, usually on the day of the audition. Art songs, lieder, and operatic arias were the required pieces, and most of the music was unfamiliar to me at the time. Working with singers is both a joy and a challenge, but this situation was always particularly demanding.

Included in these auditions were applicants for the Community Educa-

tion Division, and I played for these as well. One of the most amusing events in my career occurred during one of these auditions. A young soprano came into the room. She was prepared to sing the "Waltz" from Lehar's *The Merry Widow*. She couldn't find the edition from which she had learned the piece, so she gave me a different edition and proceeded to ask, rather innocently, "If I sing this in German, can you play it in French?" After a moment of silence, I responded that at Eastman we were taught to play in any language, so she

The piano is one of the most versatile instruments. But are pianists trained to be versatile?

needn't worry. The audition proceeded smoothly after that, but the laughter erupted when she left the room. This singer could have been devastated by a caustic remark. A calm reassurance, however, was all she needed to sing her audition. The following year, another young performer sang "Dido's Lament" during her audition. I had to play the piece with four beats to the bar, not the three that Purcell had written. She had mislearned the piece, and it was my duty to make her sound as good as I could, in spite of the incorrect reading.

Continuing to work with instrumentalists and singers has provided many hours of fulfillment, hard work, and performing opportunities. At this point I have collaborated with every voice type, including countertenor and male soprano, and just about every instrument, including some rarities like castanets and euphonium. Because the piano is so versatile, it can be used with almost any instrument, although some combinations are better than others. The complete control that the pianist needs when working with some of these diverse instruments is incredible. Dynamics have to be feathery light with a double bass, but can thunder with a trombone. Even voices need extraordi-

nary dynamics at times. I recently played some auditions for the National Symphony Orchestra, and I couldn't play loud enough for one particular singer!

The range of collaboration that constitutes my schedule includes recital work, auditions, coaching opera singers, and working with choruses. Since time is limited, the recital work that I do is primarily with professionals. I make time in my schedule with the Education Program of the NSO, however, to work with extraordinarily talented instrumentalists who are studying with symphony musicians. They perform in recitals at the Kennedy Center for the Performing Arts and in master classes with renowned musicians.

Playing auditions for instrumentalists and singers is also an excellent way to learn new literature. At one time I entertained the possibility of becoming an opera conductor, so I learned as much as I could about operas. Although my career didn't move in that direction, I'm able to use that information to work with singers and to provide feedback about their performances. A first priority of an opera coach is to be familiar with languages and stylistic elements of the opera, as well as to have an excellent ear for listening to the singer while playing the orchestral score. I had French and German training in school and, on my own, learned Italian and Spanish.

To work with choruses, the skills to master include sight-reading, score-reading, choral score-reading (SATB, SSA, TTBB, for example), flexibility, and even conducting. I mention conducting because any pianist who works with choruses needs to read the mind of the conductor. Having conducting skill and/or experience, therefore, is a necessity. The pianist's role is to provide a full range of services including harmonic support, individual vocal part reinforcement, and reduction of an orchestral score for rehearsal purposes—all at the drop of a hat. Expediting the rehearsal procedure and not holding up the flow is a constant challenge. Throughout the rehearsal, the pianist has to be one step ahead of the conductor. As pianist with The United States Army Chorus and the Choral Arts Society of Washington, I have the additional responsibilities of conducting and leading rehearsals.

Whatever the size and scope of the ensemble, supporting and complementing the sound is a constant challenge. I must admit, however, that the thrill of providing a full-blown orchestral reduction for an ensemble of 150 using the full resources, capabilities, and colors of the piano is next to none!

My conducting study has helped immeasurably during my career. Not only is conducting oneself a useful practice technique since it aids in refining interpretation, but several jobs have been offered to me in which it was necessary to conduct. At the beginning of my career, I worked in a professional musical theater and conducted many of the shows from the piano. I was also the musical director and conductor for the

Georgetown University Law Center's Gilbert and Sullivan Society. (This is the only theater group that I know of that has its own law school. Lawyers seem to be natural actors!)

A few years later I ended up conducting a performance at Wolf Trap with Victor Borge, Robert Merrill, and the Wolf Trap Orchestra. The annual gala was to feature Borge, and I had been hired to coordinate the musical aspects of the performance. In one week I had to make sure that musicians were hired and scores were ready for the performance. At the last minute, an arrangement of "Autumn Leaves" (for Merrill and the orchestra) was needed, so I provided the arrangement. At the dress rehearsal, it became clear that no one was ready to conduct

that piece as well as Debussy's *Clair de Lune* which Borge was to play with the orchestra. So Borge invited me to the stage and asked me to conduct. I thoroughly enjoyed the experience of working with these two fine performers in a different capacity than that to which I was accustomed. The performance was taped by PBS, and one of the greatest ironies of my life is that I viewed the broadcast for the first time while I was in basic training for the Army at Fort Knox. While in the hospital recuperating from a broken foot, I saw the program on television. What a strange juxtaposition—lying in bed with a broken foot, head nearly shaved, and 20 pounds lighter, watching the TV image of myself with all that hair and weight!

Many people are curious as to what my job in the Army entails. My primary duty is to accompany the Army Chorus, but the job also includes playing keyboard parts (piano, harpsichord, and electronic) with the Concert Band and Orchestra, playing background music for dinners and private parties, accompanying various singers in solo and ensemble performances (everything from Broadway to opera), and performing concertos with the band and orchestra. An additional duty is to take care of the keyboard instruments that are currently in use, making sure that they are tuned and maintained for performances, rehearsals, and recording sessions. Occasionally the organization performs on tour, but the majority of our work is here in Washington, DC as we are considered a ceremonial unit for the President. A typical schedule consists of rehearsals in the morning with performances scattered throughout the day or evening, including weekends. Performances can be as short as five minutes or be full-length concerts. There are usually three or four engagements that the Army Chorus fills each week. The rest of the time can be used for practice, further study, or off-duty employment.

Although we sing many masterpieces of choral literature, a good deal of the music we perform is in the popular vein. For popular and musical theater styles, it's helpful to be able to read pop chord symbols, transpose, and have a good theoretical knowledge. In this type of music, the singer has the melody, so I leave it out entirely, and

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MISCELLANEOUS

- Arranger
- Composer
- Music coordinator
- Concert series organizer or
administrator
- Newspaper/periodical reviewer
- Public relations (writing press
releases, biographies, program
notes)

play just the basic accompaniment or create a counter melody, a skill akin to orchestrating at the piano. Musical theater scores are reductions; the actual notes on the page are not sacrosanct, but the improvisation and re-writing should be kept within the harmonic framework provided by the composer. I learned this skill from an aunt who is a musician. During my younger years, she shared with me an approach to popular music that I now employ in my professional career. It involved reading the

The complete control that the pianist needs when working with diverse instruments is incredible.

chord symbol and the melody, and then filling in the harmony and rhythm of the accompaniment by using your ear and theoretical knowledge. At first it was difficult, but now such re-orchestrating at the piano is second nature.

From this step, it's natural to start improvising. Although I'm not versed in jazz theory and techniques, it's fun to play around in this idiom (something like singing in the shower). I just don't often do it in public. Improvising within traditional harmonic frameworks (both concert-type and popular styles), however, is completely within my realm. It's a skill that I rely on to learn both concerto accompaniments and popular songs. This also leads to being able to read lead-sheets, supplying rhythm and harmony to a single melody line. And this translates into being able to work in a combo, as a cocktail pianist in a hotel, or as a keyboardist in a jazz band.

Two years ago I completed the requirements for the D.M.A. in Chamber Music from The Catholic University of America. The decision to pursue this degree in chamber music was influenced by two factors: another piano performance degree seemed superflu-

ous, and the chamber music program at Catholic is headed by Marilyn Neeley, who guided me through the M.M. degree at Shenandoah Conservatory. I wanted to continue the working relationship. I had also been offered a position with the Chamber Artists of Washington, a professional group of musicians that performs chamber music, and my experience with chamber music was not as extensive as my solo performance and accompanying experience. Moreover, I had a strong desire to explore a further aspect of playing the piano, especially with other musicians. My association with the Chamber Artists of Washington continues to the present, and we give four or five concerts each year.

A week is never the same in this business, but there are some events that are fairly constant throughout the year. After practicing in the morning, I rehearse with the Army and teach piano at American University. One night a week is spent with the Choral Arts Society of Washington, usually playing for a rehearsal, and sometimes conducting it. In a typical month, public performances might also include chamber music performances, solo recitals, accompanying various singers and instrumentalists in recital, and playing concertos. Occasionally an opportunity arises to perform outside the Washington, DC area. In recent years, I've traveled to Spain to present concerts with Carmen de Vicente, a well-known Spanish castanet artist. A concert year can include just about any combination of musical challenges—from playing on the concert stage to performing in a private home, with music ranging from the most demanding concert literature to Broadway tunes.

My current season includes a May concert that promises to be unique—an event featuring the various pianists that work for The United States Army Band. Pianists rarely play together, so we've organized a few concerts featuring ten performers and five concert grands. Various combinations will be presented—Schubert and Brahms four-hand pieces, arrangements for five players of classical favorites, and the grand finale with all ten pianists. Nothing sounds quite like 100 fingers playing the *Stars and Stripes Forever!* ♣

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